

Using SIONlib for Multi-petaflop/Exascale POSIX I/O in BONSAI

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Abstract

This white paper describes a project to modify the I/O of the Bonsai astrophysics code to scale up to more than 10,000 nodes on the Titan system. A remaining bottleneck is the I/O: the creation of separate files for each MPI task overloads the Lustre metadata server. The use of the SIONlib library on the Lustre filesystem of different PRACE systems is investigated. Several issues had to be resolved, both with the SIONlib library and the Liblustre API, before a satisfactory I/O performance could be achieved. SIONlib reaches about half the performance of a naive approach where each MPI task writes a separate file for a few thousand MPI tasks. However, when more MPI tasks are used, the SIONlib library shows the same performance as the naive approach. The SIONlib library exhibits both the performance and the scalability that is needed to be successful at exascale.

Introduction

Gravity forces drive the formation of structures in the universe. The long-range nature of gravity makes it a key physical process at all length scales, from dust particles to cosmological structures. Gravitational manybody simulations are used to investigate and explain the structure and dynamics of the universe. A galaxy contains about 100 billion stars/particles. About 96% of the universe is made up of dark matter, and 4% consists of visible matter (stars, etc.).

Bonsai is a gravitational N-body tree-code that runs completely on the GPU [1]. This reduces the amount of time spent on communication with the CPU. The Bonsai code has been proven to scale up to nearly the full size of the Titan system at ORNL, which has 18,688 GPU nodes. It has been written using C++. Unfortunately, one bottleneck is still the I/O, which is discussed in more detail in the next section.

The increase of the I/O performance of HPC systems has not kept the same trend as the computing capabilities. On top of that, users have not been able to squeeze as much performance from parallel file systems as they have from computational hardware. Also, on most HPC systems users get exclusive computing resources, whereas the file system is normally shared between all jobs. Many of the applications that have already been run on PRACE infrastructure, are limited by I/O bottlenecks. Also due to the increasing observational datasets from many scientific fields, these problems are not foreseen to be solved in the near future. The International Exascale Software Project noted that “I/O should be an integral activity to be optimized while architecting the system and the underlying software.”

Unfortunately, it is difficult to get a good performance from most current parallel I/O libraries for structured file formats. Libraries like PnetCDF and HDF5 have reached only modest I/O bandwidths of 1-2Gb/s or even less in

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production codes [2]. It is unclear how the performance can be increased significantly, due to the unknown impact of the multiple layers from the API to the file system.

Due to the simple I/O structures that are used and the required high I/O performance in Bonsai, the SIONlib library was selected. Two of the main advantages of the SIONlib library are its proven performance and scalability on some of the largest systems in the world [3,4] and its non-intrusiveness: the open and close calls are specific, while the reading and writing of the data can in theory still be done with the standard C fread and fwrite calls. SIONlib does contain some extra routines for reading and writing that provide some more functionality, e.g. checking for available space in the allocated blocks.

SIONlib uses the stripe size on the Lustre filesystem as a natural boundary in the file format. Each MPI rank gets its own set of stripes for writing. This circumvents the performance bottlenecks due to locking, which is often a cause of poor performance when using other file formats. The Lustre FAQ remarks that larger stripe sizes exacerbate performance problems due to increased locking [5], but this can be ignored for SIONlib. The downside of a larger stripe size in SIONlib is that disk space is reserved for an MPI task, which might not be used. Stripe size can therefore be seen as a tuning parameter, where a larger stripe size gives higher bandwidth, but more overhead in the file size.

Technical background Bonsai

Bonsai uses separate output files for each MPI task, which shows a good I/O performance for moderate task counts. However, it puts a huge strain on the filesystem in terms of the number of metadata operations, most importantly open and creation of files. Therefore, this strategy doesn't scale to thousands of MPI tasks. The creation of thousands of files on Titan could hang the whole system for a few minutes. This problem exacerbates quickly when scaling up Bonsai to the full Titan system.

Most of the computation in Bonsai is on the GPU. The CPU is only used for coordination of the simulation:

- 1 core for MPI,
- 1 core to control the GPU,
- the remaining cores are used for work that has to be prepared to be sent and received by the MPI thread.

Few of the cores can be used for data-writing.

The largest simulation would require about 1PB of data to be written in 1 week. The output consists of start dumps and snapshots. The start dumps will need to contain all information for all particles, both stars and dark matter particles. The load balancing algorithm distributes the particles across processes reasonably uniformly and the I/O load will therefore also be balanced. Due to load-balancing, the number of particles per process is different (and varies per time-step). However the difference between the different processes is at most 50%. The average will be around 16 million, with highest numbers around 19 to 20 million. The number of particles is limited by the available GPU memory.

The snapshots will only contain the information for the stars, since the dark matter particles are usually not interesting for analysis. This is about 4% of the total number of particles. The types of particles are inhomogeneously distributed across the universe, where stars are clustered into e.g. galaxies. The I/O per process for a snapshot is therefore inhomogeneous: some MPI domains will have only star particles (inside galaxies) and others will have only dark matter particles (outside galaxies).

At the moment, Bonsai writes data in the tipsy data format, which consists of:

1. a small header with the following fields:

```
struct dump {
    double time ;
    int nbodies ;
    int ndim ;
    int nsph ;
    int ndark ;           // the nr. of dark matter particles
    int nstar ;          // the nr. of star particles
} ;
```

2. records for dark matter particles:

```
struct dark_particle {
    Real mass;
    Real pos[MAXDIM];
```

```

    Real vel[MAXDIM];
    Real eps;
    int phi ;           // the ID of the particle
} ;

```

3. and records for stars:

```

struct star_particle {
    Real mass;
    Real pos[MAXDIM];
    Real vel[MAXDIM];
    Real metals ;           // not used by Bonsai
    Real tform ;           // not used by Bonsai
    Real eps;
    int phi ;               // in Bonsai: the ID of the particle
} ;

```

Assuming that MAXDIM=3, the dark matter particle record is 36 bytes and a star particle record is 44 bytes.

The performance requirements for the I/O necessitate some changes to the file format. Each process writes its data according to the above definitions into the SIONlib file, so each process writes its own header and the data structures for the different types of particles. To keep the output size as small as possible, the fields that are not used by Bonsai will be removed from the above structures.

Post-processing

The files could be read for post-processing in several ways:

1. read and analyze all data in a snapshot or dump. The SIONlib file(s) can be read either serially or in parallel.
2. read and analyze data for a particle type. The SIONlib file has for every rank a header with the number of particles for each different type, from which the position can be calculated where the particle type can be found.
3. read and analyze a specific particle. The records in the tipsy format contain the particle ID and the IDs are therefore scattered over the output, which is inefficient for searching. The Topsy format can be modified to separate the particle IDs from the above structures and first write a list with the particle IDs. Searching for the particle ID then only requires to read about 10% of the file.
4. analyze specific regions in the universe. Each MPI rank represents a different region of the universe and can be analyzed as such.

The creation of a global index of particles during the simulation is unfeasible, since it would require too much global communication and single-node memory. However, it could be done efficiently as a post-processing step.

Test systems

All systems that were used for benchmarking have a Lustre filesystem. The parallel I/O performance of the Lustre file system is due to a distributed file organization across a number of Object Storage Targets (or OSTs). Normally, files are placed round robin over the OSTs to create a well-balanced I/O. To reach a higher I/O performance, files can also be spread across multiple OSTs, also called 'striping'. The Lustre file system can separately lock each stripe of a file.

The OST values are outlined below for the systems used.

- Cartesius: 572 compute nodes, 48 OSTs for /scratch
- Curie: 5,544 compute nodes, 160 OSTs for \$SCRATCHDIR
- Hermit: 3,552 compute nodes, 96 OSTs for work directory
- Titan: 18,688 compute nodes, 1,008 OSTs for scratch

It clearly shows that the Titan system is an order of magnitude larger than any of the systems that are available in PRACE. The number of OSTs is not a direct indicator of the I/O performance, but it shows how wide the files can be striped on different systems.

Optimizations

Several optimizations were required to achieve a good performance with SIONlib.

Opening the SIONlib file

First benchmarks on Cartesius with sionlib 1.3p7 show a considerable time for creating and opening a SIONlib file that is striped across all 48 OSTs, see figure 1. The creation and opening time for 720 MPI tasks on 60 nodes is 13s. The time increases linearly with the number of OSTs that the file is striped over and the number of MPI tasks that open the file together. This approach will not scale to the Titan system, with 20 times more OSTs and over 10.000 MPI tasks.

Figure 1: Time for creation and opening of a shared file on 48 OSTs with SIONlib when using ANSI I/O on Cartesius.

The SIONlib library uses by default the ANSI I/O calls (fopen, fread, fwrite, fclose), which is normally a good choice due to its buffering. However, for the parallel opening of files on Cartesius, this is a poor choice. The SIONlib library can also use the POSIX I/O calls (open, close), which doesn't show the poor scaling behavior that is shown in figure 1. An Investigation of the reason for this poor scaling behavior of the ANSI fopen call using the ltrace-command (with the -S -T flags) shows the following:

POSIX open:

```
000: open("partest_parfile.dat", O_RDWR|O_CREAT, 0664) = 43 <0.002094>
002: open("partest_parfile.dat", O_RDWR) = 49 <0.000397>
```

ANSI fopen:

```
297: open("partest_parfile.dat", O_WRONLY|O_CREAT|O_TRUNC, 0666) = 22 <0.972891>
305: open("partest_parfile.dat", O_WRONLY|O_CREAT|O_TRUNC, 0666) = 22 <0.996052>
```

where the first number is the MPI rank and the numbers in brackets denote the time in seconds spent inside the open system call. (Note that the ANSI fopen call also uses the POSIX interface for its I/O.) The POSIX open implementation creates the file with the first rank, while all other ranks just open the file. The ANSI fopen call tries to create or truncate the file, which results in a poor scaling behavior. The ANSI fopen call in routine `_sion_file_open_ansi_write_existing` (file `src/lib/sion_file.c`) can be modified to use the 'r+' mode, which allows writing, but does not create or truncate the file. This information is communicated to the developers and will be included in the next release (the current release is 1.4p3) if this functions correctly in SIONlib.

SIONlib buffering

As a result of the poor performance of the ANSI interface, the POSIX interface was used for this study. The POSIX interface is unbuffered and therefore requires large writes to achieve a good performance. The Bonsai

application uses writes of single records of particles and a buffering layer is therefore required. Luckily, SIONlib implements an (undocumented) buffering scheme. This can be enabled by setting the environment variable SION_BUFFERSIZE (in this study set to 1048576) and using the following options to open the file:

```
sid = sion_paropen_mpi(myfname, "wb,posix,buffered", &nfiles, comm,
                      &lComm, &chunksize, &blksize, &myrank, &fptr, &newfname);
```

The SIONlib buffer is not flushed at the moment that the file is closed. A routine was added to SIONlib to flush the buffer explicitly before closing the file. Also this change will be included in the next release.

Lustre striping

To write in parallel to a single file with a high I/O performance on Lustre, it is necessary to stripe the file across multiple OSTs. The aggregate bandwidth of the OSTs sets the maximum I/O speed that can be reached. This can be done using the following command:

```
lfs setstripe [-s stripe-size ] [-c stripe count] <directory|filename>
```

which can be used to set the stripe count and the stripe size of files that are not yet created. For directories, this sets a default for files in that directory that are not yet created. For more information, see 'man lfs'. Although this is a convenient command for incidental use, it is not very convenient to use in an HPC application: the application can run for a long time and the user would need to explicitly set striping information for all output files beforehand.

The liblustre library provides an API for users to get and change the striping of files from within the code. For more information, see 'man liblustreapi'. The llapi_file_create call provides the same functionality as the 'lfs setstripe' command. Unfortunately, documentation is incorrect for Lustre production versions (2.1.6 on Cartesius): not all the include files exist, nor are they needed. The only needed include file is <lustre/liblustreapi.h> for a C-program. Unfortunately, the include files do not mix well with C++. Therefore, the following explicit definition, copied from the file /usr/include/lustre/liblustreapi.h, was used in the code:

```
extern "C" {
int llapi_file_create(const char *name, unsigned long long stripe_size,
                    int stripe_offset, int stripe_count,
                    int stripe_pattern);
}
```

The liblustre library can be linked with the flag '-llustreapi'. More recent releases should have fixed (some of) the above issues, but that wasn't checked.

Performance tests: I/O bandwidth

With the first experiment it is tested if the SIONlib library can reach sufficient I/O bandwidth for the Bonsai application. The I/O needs to be fast enough to write all data to disk before the next I/O event of the running application. HPC resources are wasted when waiting for I/O, which is especially a problem for large-scale jobs. For this test, every MPI task writes 5 million star particles to disk. To mimic the Bonsai use case, we use 1 MPI task per node.

Figure 2: Bandwidth on Cartesius for the naive approach and SIONlib writing to 1 file, using different stripe sizes (in MB). All runs with 1 MPI task per node. Error bars indicate the standard deviation from 8 measurements.

Figure 2 shows the bandwidth on Cartesius for SIONlib and a separate file per MPI task ('naive approach'). Different lustre stripe sizes were used for SIONlib. The naive approach sets the lustre stripe count to 1, so the file is placed on a single OST to limit the metadata overhead per file. This is the default on Cartesius, but other systems often use a default stripe count of 4 (e.g. Hermit or Titan) or 8. Note that setting the lustre stripe count to 1 is already a significant optimization of the naive approach: the longest opening time for 4096 files on Curie is only 3ms with stripe count 1, where it is 1.4s for files with stripe count 4. The different files are still spread over the available OSTs, effectively still utilising all bandwidth with stripe count 1.

It is clear that the naive approach offers the best write bandwidth for these modest MPI sizes. The default stripe size of 1MB shows a performance of about half of the naive approach. The optimal stripe size is around 6-8MB, with 20-30% more bandwidth. Larger stripe sizes don't achieve a higher bandwidth.

Note, however, that a larger stripe size will also increase file size, since SIONlib will reserve stripe sized chunks for each rank. If e.g. the stripe size is 16MB and the MPI task only writes 1MB, the other 15MB will be wasted. With a stripe size of 8MB, the overhead in disk space is about 3%.

The figure also shows that the scalability of SIONlib levels off beyond 96 tasks. The maximum bandwidth that can be expected under ideal circumstances on Cartesius is over 20GB/s, but these tests have been run in the production environment with other jobs using the filesystem as well.

Measurements on the PRACE Tier-0 Hermit system in figure 3 show some interesting differences. The variability is high and there is no discernible difference in bandwidth between the naive approach and the different stripe sizes. Furthermore, there is no indication that the Hermit system with 96 OSTs can sustain a higher bandwidth than the Cartesius system with 48 OSTs. This could be caused by intermittent load from other jobs, possibly exacerbated by the less favorable (higher) ratio of nodes/OST on Hermit.

Measurements on the Titan system in figure 4 show that SIONlib reaches 25%-40% of the maximum performance of the naive approach. All measurements were done with a stripe size of 1MB and it is expected that the performance for SIONlib will still increase for a larger stripe size.

Figure 3: Bandwidth measurements on PRACE Tier-0 Hermit with 64 nodes, 1 MPI task per node. The bars are averages of 8 measurements with minimum and maximum values indicated by the error bars.

Figure 4: Bandwidth on Titan for the naive approach and SIONlib writing to 1 file, using 1MB stripe size. All runs with 1 MPI task per node.

Scalability with many MPI tasks

The second experiment is to test the scalability with the number of MPI tasks. A bottleneck that has shown up on large-scale systems is the number of tasks per shared file, caused by meta-data synchronization between OSTs during writing [6]. A maximum bandwidth to the Lustre file system seems to be reached with only a handful of nodes per OST. However, the runs on Bonsai will include over ten thousand MPI tasks and it is not clear if that maximum bandwidth can still be achieved when writing to a file with that many tasks.

Unfortunately, the PRACE infrastructure does not have a system similar to Titan, with a Lustre file system and more than ten thousand nodes available. Therefore, we use all cores of the nodes on PRACE systems to increase the total number of MPI tasks. It is expected that the maximum bandwidth does not decrease, even if thousands of tasks are used.

Figure 5: Write bandwidth on Curie for fully populated nodes with the naive approach and SIONlib using different stripe sizes.

Figure 5 shows the results from a test on Curie. Again, the naive approach shows the highest write bandwidths, reaching over 18Gb/s for 256 MPI tasks. At the same time it shows the detrimental impact of writing too many files, where SIONlib catches up when using thousands of tasks. However, the different measurements for SIONlib do show that there are large variations for SIONlib, which are probably caused by congestion due to the shared nature of the file system. It still seems that the naive approach is a good approach to reach a high I/O bandwidth, even up to 5,000 cores.

Figure 6: Write bandwidth on Hermit for fully populated nodes with the naive approach and SIONlib using different stripe sizes.

Figure 6 shows some results from the PRACE Tier-0 Hermit system, scaling up to 16.384 cores. This is close to the MPI task count for the largest anticipated production simulations. It shows several things: the scalability and performance of the SIONlib library is on par with the naive approach, so neither of the two I/O methods hit bottlenecks at this scale. The variations in performance show no clear pattern and are more likely due to the congestion of the shared file system than due to the used parameters. Also, the absolute bandwidths are probably not representative for the use case that we are interested in: all cores are used for writing and this might cause congestion in the network between the nodes and the file system.

An alternative solution that was proposed in [4] is to create one file per OST, each with a stripe count of 1. This balances the metadata traffic due to file creation and due to parallel access: it distributes the I/O load equally over all available OSTs, without overloading the metadata server when there are many more MPI tasks than OSTs. Luckily, the SIONlib library features the creation of multi-file output transparently. The SIONlib library can divide all MPI tasks across the available files, either automatically or manually. Advantages are that the file sizes are more manageable (Gigabytes instead of Terabytes) and that in case of failure of one OST, only the files on that OST are lost. On the other hand, the user has more files to handle and needs to ensure that the files are kept together.

Reading the data

Reading of the output files is done for two main reasons: to restart the simulation and to analyze the output. A restart dump needs to be read as fast as possible, to minimize the time for checkpoint restarts. This is not a problem, since the read bandwidth is easily exhausted by a handful of nodes. Neither any metadata updates, nor any locking is needed to read the file.

The analysis of the output data is usually much less time-critical, although the size of the output demands that it can be read efficiently and in parallel. Reading can be done either serially or in parallel. If the file is read in parallel, every MPI task opens the file as if it was a serial process. The number of MPI tasks that read the file can be different from the number of tasks that wrote the file. The `sion_open_rank()` function allows an MPI task to open the data for any MPI task. E.g. rank 0 will open the SION file and open the chunks for rank 0. The function `sion_get_locations()` then returns the number of MPI tasks that wrote the SION file or files. This number can be distributed across all available MPI tasks for parallel reading. This can be used for a flexible and parallel analysis of these datasets. Note that the use of the multi-file option in SIONlib is transparent to the user in terms of API. The user just opens the main file with the rank ID and SIONlib selects the corresponding file with the data.

Conclusions

I/O is often a major bottleneck for HPC applications. Two approaches have been compared to write data to a Lustre file system in parallel. The first method is the naive approach, where each MPI task creates and writes its own output file. The second method is the SIONlib library, which creates one file and gives every MPI task a file pointer and a specified number of file blocks to write in parallel into the same file. The SIONlib library has the advantage that it minimizes the metadata traffic due to creation of files and that the number of output files is manageable, even for jobs with many thousands of MPI tasks.

The results show that the naive approach is a good method for reaching a high I/O bandwidth, even when using thousands of MPI tasks. One optimization is to set the lustre stripe count to 1 for all output files. It was not investigated when the Lustre file system breaks down due to metadata traffic overload. The downside of the naive approach is that the user needs to manage as many output files as MPI tasks.

The SIONlib library shows a performance that is about 30-60% of the naive approach for a few thousand MPI tasks, but it has a performance that is on par with the naive approach for a larger number of MPI tasks. Furthermore, it has a large advantage that it drastically reduces the number of output files. The SIONlib library should be seriously considered, especially for applications running at many thousands MPI tasks or more.

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